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EDITORIAL NOTE

It is with immense pleasure and pride that we present to you the third issue of the Bauchi State University (BASUG) Law Journal, marking our second publication for the year. This issue stands as a testament to the tireless commitment of our contributors, whose scholarly work continues to push the boundaries of legal scholarship in Nigeria and beyond.

We are particularly elated by the diversity and depth of the submissions received for this edition, not only from across Nigeria but also from international scholars. The topics covered reflect the evolving and multifaceted nature of legal discourse in contemporary society.

These papers, among others, cover a vast range of legal fields, reflecting the dynamic interplay between law and society. We believe the breadth of scholarship featured in this issue will contribute meaningfully to academic discourse and legal practice.

We would like to extend our profound appreciation to the Faculty of Law, Sa'adu Zungur University, for their unwavering support as our publisher. Our sincere gratitude also goes to the Management of Sa'adu Zungur University for their continued encouragement and partnership in ensuring the success of this journal.

We are deeply indebted to the contributing authors for their invaluable research and dedication to advancing legal knowledge. Their work remains at the heart of what makes this journal a beacon of academic excellence.

Finally, we thank you, our esteemed readers, for your continued engagement with the BASUG Law Journal. It is through your readership that this publication finds purpose, and we hope that this issue serves as both a valuable resource and a source of inspiration for future legal thought and action.

Sincerely,

Prof. S. M. G Kanam
Chairman of Editorial Board and Dean
Faculty of Law,
Sa'adu Zungur University

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AN ASSESSMENT OF THE MEDICO-LEGAL AND ETHICAL ISSUES IN SURROGATE MOTHERHOOD

By

Agbo Friday Ojonugwa Mary Arthur Jolasinmi** Grace Perpetual Dafiel****

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ABSTRACT

Many couples have looked forward to having their own children. However, some are faced with medical difficulties which had prevented them from achieving this desire naturally. Advancement in medical and biomedical sciences through assisted reproductive technologies or techniques (ARTS) have offered infertile couples opportunities to procreate. Surrogacy arrangements happen to be one of such ART procedures. Surrogacy is an agreement by which a woman agreed to carry and deliver a child for another individual or couple. The researcher adopted the doctrinal approach having reviewed primary and secondary sources and literature to this paper. This paper examined the medico-legal and ethical issues on surrogacy motherhood in Nigeria and selected jurisdictions. It was discovered that while a number of countries have regulated the practice, Nigeria has no legislation regulating the practice thereby encouraging unethical practices. However, this paper recommended that appropriate laws should be put in place in Nigeria to protect the respective parties to the surrogate motherhood arrangement. The research reveals that it does not seem to be a problem for intended parents to acquire a baby through surrogacy arrangements, whereas the surrogate mother sometimes has to pay a high cost of exclusion by her family members and society. the study analyses societal response to the commissioning parents 'decision to opt for a surrogacy service and the surrogate mother's decision to provide a service.

Keywords: *Assessment, Medico-Legal, Surrogate, Motherhood.*

1. INTRODUCTION

After creating human beings, God instructed the man and the woman to be “Fruitful, and multiply, and replenish the earth”.¹ However, it sometimes happens that, years after marriage, some couples still experience delays in childbearing as a result of infertility. The hope of procreation in such instances becomes dwindled and abandons the couples in a state of worries, stigmatisation and constant pressures from their family members and the larger society in general. Infertility is a global phenomenon as all countries deal with it in varying degrees.² According to modern medicine, “Infertility is a disease which requires medical treatment”.³ Medically, infertility is a disease of the reproductive system defined by the inability to attain a clinical pregnancy or impregnate a woman after a year of more of regular unprotected coitus⁴ and without using contraceptives.

Over the past few decades, the practice of surrogacy has attracted attention internationally with ongoing efforts in international legal documents to ensure best practices in surrogacy. Countries approach the subject of surrogacy from different perspectives with some countries entirely prohibiting surrogacy (France, Switzerland),⁵ while other countries permit surrogacy to the extent that it is not to be commercialized.⁶ In England by the Surrogacy Arrangement Act 1985; in Hong Kong by Human Reproductive Technology Ordinance 2000; in South Africa by Ch 19 of the Children’s Act 38 of 2005. Some countries are regarded as surrogacy-friendly as they expressly allow surrogacy while other countries have no clear regulation of surrogacy.⁷

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¹ Finis Jennings Dake, Dakes’s Annotated Reference Bible (Dake Bible Sales Inc., Standard Size Edition, 2006), The Book of Genesis, Chapter 1: 27 – 28 (Kings James Version).

² Enobong Mbang Akpambang, Monica Amujo-Akomolafe, ‘International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies’ Volume 7, Issue 3, 2020, pages 18-39.

³ Zegers-Hochschild, F., ‘The International Committee for Monitoring Assisted Reproductive Technology (ICMART) and the World Health Organisation (WHO)’, (2009) 24 (11) *Human Reproduction*, 2683-2687.

⁴ Ibid, p.2686.

⁵ In France by arts 16-17 of the French Civil Code; in Switzerland by art 4 of *Bundesgesetz uber die medizinisch unterstützte Fortpflanzung* 1998.

⁶ In England by the Surrogacy Arrangement Act 1985; in Hong Kong by Human Reproductive Technology Ordinance 2000; in South Africa by Ch 19 of the Children’s Act 38 of 2005.

⁷ In Nigeria based on Practice Guidelines of the Association of Fertility and Reproductive Health (AFRH) of Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In reviewing the literature on the An Assessment of The Medico-Legal and Ethical Issues in Surrogate Motherhood some selected book will be considered first, Rachel Cook, Shelley Day Sclater, and Felicity Keganas in their book “Surrogate Motherhood: International Perspectives”⁸ The book provides a comprehensive overview of surrogate motherhood globally but lacks in-depth analysis of medicolegal and ethical issues in African countries like Nigeria. This article seeks to conduct a comparative study of medicolegal framework regulating surrogate motherhood in Nigeria and other African countries, highlighting the challenges and opportunities for improvement.

Lisa Fuller in “The Ethics of surrogate Motherhood: A Philosophical analysis”⁹ The book focuses primarily on philosophical and ethical aspects, with limited discussion of legal frameworks and their implications for surrogate mothers and children but failed to access the medicolegal issues in surrogate motherhood, however, this article explores the legal rights and protections afforded to surrogate mothers and children in Nigeria, and highlighting areas where medicolegal frameworks can be strengthened to address ethical concerns.

Kerry Petersen in “Surrogate Motherhood and the law”¹⁰ While the book provides a thorough legal analysis, it primarily focuses on western jurisdictions, and not on The Medico-Legal and Ethical Issues in Surrogate Motherhood with limited consideration of cultural and socio-economic factors influencing surrogate motherhood in non-western context like Nigeria. More also, this article seeks to investigate the cultural and socio-economic factors influencing surrogate motherhood in Nigeria, exploring how these factors intersect with medicolegal frameworks and ethical considerations.

3. THE CONCEPT AND DEVELOPMENT OF SURROGATE MOTHERHOOD

The noun, ‘*surrogate*,’ originated from the early 15th century Latin word, *surrogatus*, a past participle of *surrogate or subrogatus*, meaning, a substitute or person appointed to act in the place of another.¹¹ Surrogacy has also been defined as:

⁸Cook R, Sclater SD, Kaganas F(eds), Surrogate Motherhood: International perspectives (Hart publishing 2 003).

⁹ Fuller L, The Ethics of Surrogate Motherhood: A Philosophical Analysis (Palgrave Macmillan 2017).

¹⁰ Petersen K, Surrogate Motherhood and the Law (Routledge 2017).

¹¹ See, ‘Origin and meaning of surrogate.’ Available at <<https://www.etymonline.com/word/surrogate>. Accessed on 13th May 2 024 at 4:01pm.

Arrangement in which a woman agrees to a pregnancy, achieved through assisted reproductive technology, in which neither of the gametes belongs to her or her husband, with the intention to carry it to term and hand over the child to the person or persons for whom she is acting as a surrogate.¹²

Thus, in medical terms, surrogacy implies the use of a substitute mother to carry a pregnancy for another woman and thereafter relinquishes the child/children and any parental entitlement to the child/children to the commissioning parents or commissioning mother, usually an infertile couple.¹³

The concept of surrogacy can be traced to Biblical times.¹⁴ According to the Old Testament, Abraham's "barren" wife Sarah persuaded Abraham to have intercourse with her maid Hagar so "she may have a child by her."¹⁵ Hagar then conceived and gave birth to Ishmael, whom Sarah and Abraham raised as their own son.¹⁶ Obviously, in those days there were no "Surrogacy contracts" nor any notion that the bearer of the child should be paid a fee for carrying the child.¹⁷ Furthermore, it was never disputed that the bearer of the child would relinquish her parental rights upon the birth of the child.¹⁸

As society and reproductive technology advanced, the concept of surrogacy became more widely recognised. With the creation of procedures such as artificial insemination and *in vitro* fertilisation, surrogacy became a viable alternative means of reproduction for infertile couples.¹⁹ Before surrogacy became the centre of the current legal debate, many informal surrogacy arrangements existed, in which a woman, usually a friend or relative of the infertile couple, would carry and deliver a child for an infertile couple for purely charitable reasons.²⁰ In these arrangements, surrogates were rarely screened, and a requirement that the parties sign a contract usually was

¹² The Assisted Reproductive Technology (Regulation) Bill 2008, India

¹³ n.2

¹⁴ Christine L. Kerian, "Surrogacy: A Last Resort Alternative for Infertile Women or a Commodification of Women's Bodies and Children?" (1997) *Wis. Women's L.J.* 113, 116-17

¹⁵ The Holy Bible, Genesis 16:1-2, *King James Version*.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ Julia J. Tate, "Surrogacy: What Progress Since Hagar, Bilhah, and Zilpah!" 1 (1994).

¹⁸ *Ibid.* The fact that Hagar was Sarah's "maid" may further the notion that surrogacy is a form of A.

¹⁹ n.11

²⁰ Susan L. Cooper, et al "Beyond Infertility", (1994) *DePaul Journal of Health Care Law* 261

not present.²¹ Furthermore, in response to concerns about violating “baby selling” statutes, which were enacted to regulate black market adoptions, surrogates were almost never paid a fee.²²

There are basically two types of surrogacy, namely, traditional surrogacy and gestational surrogacy.²³

- (i) Traditional surrogacy requires an artificial insemination of the sperm of the intended father or sperm of donor into the surrogate.²⁴ It could also mean a process whereby the egg of the surrogate is used; as a result, the surrogate mother is genetically related to the resulting child.²⁵
- (ii) Gestational surrogacy on the other hand is an arrangement where the embryo is fertilised with the egg of the intending mother and the sperm of the intending father (though donor eggs, donor embryos, or donor sperm are sometimes used) and implanted into the surrogate mother. In this instance, the baby is not genetically related to the surrogate mother.²⁶

Under the United Kingdom laws, the legal mother is unambiguous in both partial and full surrogacies. Section 33 of the Human Fertilisation and Embryology Act confirms that the surrogate is the legal mother. It states:

The woman who is carrying or has carried a child as a result of the placing in her of an embryo or of sperm and egg, and no other women, is to be treated as the mother of the child. ²⁷

Section 47 further states that “A woman cannot be treated as the mother as a result of egg donation”.²⁸ In some countries, legal and genetic motherhood are synonymous, while others may argue the woman who raised the child is the mother.

²¹ Ibid.

²² John D. Ingram, “Surrogate Gestator: A New and Honourable Profession, (1993) 76 Marq. L. Rev. 675, 681.82

²³ Lones, M.E., “A Christian Ethical Perspective on Surrogacy,” (2016) 2 (1) *Bioethics in Faith and Practice*, p.23.

²⁴ Rozee, V. et al, “Gestational Surrogacy in India”. Available at <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309769094_Gestational_surrogate_in_India. Accessed on 13 May 2024 at 5:53pm.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ HFEA 2008

²⁸ Ibid

Children born by intercourse between two consenting adults (i.e. between the surrogate and the husband/partner of the commissioning couple) falls outside of this law.

4. THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN SURROGATE MOTHERHOOD

The precedent for modern surrogate motherhood was set in California in the mid-1970s.²⁹ At this time, a couple placed an anonymous advertisement in a local paper in order to find a woman to bear a child for them through artificial insemination.³⁰ When a woman answered the advertisement and agreed to become the surrogate, the couple's attorney drafted a contract in which the couple agreed to pay the surrogate \$7,000 for her "Services" and \$3,000 in medical and legal expenses.³¹ The pregnancy that resulted from this agreement produced a baby girl.³² When the couple's story appeared in the Detroit Free Press, another infertile couple approached Noel Keane, the "father of surrogate motherhood",³³ in Michigan and requested he help them find a woman who bear a child for them.³⁴ Although Keane was hesitant to enter into such an uncharted area of the law, he construed the aforementioned California arrangement as precedent and decided to help this couple and two others.³⁵

In order to determine the parameters of the relevant law in Michigan, Keane wrote letters to the State Attorney General, a judge, and a physician.³⁶ Only the judge replied.³⁷ The judge opined that, under Michigan law, the impregnation of women through artificial insemination was wholly acceptable and that the payment of medical and legal fees was equally legitimate.³⁸ Nevertheless, the judge reasoned that the intended parents of the child could not legally pay the surrogate a fee to carry the child or to relinquish the child for adoption.³⁹ Under these circumstances, Keane encountered great difficulty in finding surrogates for the three couples because,

²⁹ Noel P. Keane, *et al*, "The Surrogate Mother (1981) 33-35.

³⁰ *Ibid* at 33.

³¹ *Ibid*.

³² *Ibid*.

³³ Lori B. Andrews, *et al* "Between Strangers: Surrogate Mothers, Expectant Fathers, & Brave New Babies (1989) 16.

³⁴ *n.20*.

³⁵ *Ibid*, at 46-48

³⁶ *Ibid*.

³⁷ *Ibid*.

³⁸ *Ibid*.

³⁹ *Ibid*.

according to State law, these surrogates would not be compensated for undergoing artificial insemination, carrying a baby for nine months, and releasing the child upon birth.⁴⁰ In 1978, after appealing to the public's sense of altruism by publicising the plight of these couples,⁴¹ each of them had babies through surrogacy arrangements.⁴² Despite these success stories, Keane's primary objective was to arrange for the legal payment of fees to surrogate mothers.⁴³ To this end, he attempted to determine a method by which to circumvent the Michigan adoption statutes, which prohibited payment of money to a mother for relinquishing her rights to her child.⁴⁴ Thus, in representing an infertile couple in *Doe v Kelley*,⁴⁵ Keane unsuccessfully challenged these laws.⁴⁶ In this case, the Michigan Court of Appeal held that, even though a couple might legally use a surrogate to conceive a child, any payment made to the surrogate in exchange for the release of her parental rights to the child was illegal under state law.⁴⁷

In view of Michigan's Hard Line Rejection of Compensation For Surrogates, Keane decided to work with a clinic in Kentucky, where the payment to a woman for the relinquishment of her parental rights to a child had not been prohibited.⁴⁸ As part of his work, Keane sent Michigan couples to Kentucky, where they established residency, completed adoption proceedings, and paid the surrogate mother \$10,000 for the "services".⁴⁹ These procedures made Keane's practice of arranging surrogacy agreements highly successful,⁵⁰ and helped popularise surrogacy as a viable solution to infertility.⁵¹

In the 1980s, surrogacy became a prominent practice in California and many other States.⁵² In addition to its newfound popularity, the technological aspect of surrogacy

⁴⁰ n.24.

⁴¹ *Ibid*, at 28.

⁴² *Ibid*, at 95, 115.

⁴³ *Ibid*, 31, at 116.

⁴⁴ *Ibid*.

⁴⁵ (1981)307NW 2d438.

⁴⁶ *Ibid*.

⁴⁷ *Ibid*.

⁴⁸ n.24.

⁴⁹ n.20.

⁵⁰ *Ibid*.

⁵¹ *Ibid*, at 119.

⁵² *Ibid*.

expanded with the success of the first gestational surrogacy arrangement in 1986.⁵³ By the mid-1980's, however, the growth and success of surrogacy arrangements was thwarted by legal battles and controversies.⁵⁴

4.0 THE FEMINIST DEBATE OVER SURROGATE MOTHERHOOD

Although the issues surrounding surrogacy have been debated in a number of religious, economic, ethical, and moral contexts,⁵⁵ the most impassioned debates concerning the morality and legality of surrogacy was held among feminists. Since the second wave of the feminist movement in 1910, feminists have argued that women have a constitutional right to control their own bodies, and therefore, have the right to procreate, to use contraception, or to abort.⁵⁶ With the advent of new reproductive technologies, however, a number of different choices have arisen. While some feminists view these new choices as reproductive freedoms, others view them as vehicles for the exploitation of women. Thus, feminists are widely divided on the issues surrounding surrogate motherhood.

The role of women in society historically has been defined by the biological fact that only women can bear children.⁵⁷ Since men have exercised control over women's bodies and reproductive capacities, some feminists fear that men will use surrogacy in order to further their control over women's bodies for their own needs.⁵⁸ They also fear that the use of the new reproductive technologies will infringe upon women's autonomy and that their reproductive capacities will be employed to further the interests of a male-dominated society.

Liberal feminists advocate a woman's reproductive choice and freedom to contract.⁵⁹ They opined that women should be free to choose among the various reproductive alternatives, including surrogacy, as long as this choice does not harm anyone in the

⁵³ Jamie Levitt, "Biology, Technology, and Genealogy: A Proposed Uniform Surrogacy Legislation, (1992) 25 *Colum. J.L. & Soc. Probs.* 451, 455

⁵⁴ n.42.

⁵⁵ n.25.

⁵⁶ Lori B. Andrews, "Surrogate Motherhood: The Challenges for Feminists, in *Surrogate Motherhood: Politics and Privacy*, (1990) (Larry Gostin ed., 167, 168

⁵⁷ Norman J. Wikler, "Society's Response to the New Reproductive Technologies: The Feminist Perspective, (1986) 59 *Cal. L. Rev.* 1043, 1043.

⁵⁸ Gena Corea, "*The Mother Machine: Reproductive Technologies from Artificial Insemination to Artificial Womb* (1985) 283-88.

⁵⁹ Rosemarie Tong, "*Feminist Perspective and Gestational Motherhood: The Search for a Unified Legal focus*, in *Reproduction, Ethics and the Law: Feminist Perspective* (1995) 55, 69, Joan C. Callahan, Ed.

process.⁶⁰ According to liberal feminist theory, the protection of a woman's constitutional rights to privacy and procreation is the foremost priority.⁶¹ Therefore, liberal feminists view surrogacy as a positive practice because it ensures the preservation of these rights in such a way that all parties ultimately will benefit.⁶² The surrogate "achieves fulfilment by giving the gift of life to the infertile couple and the couple also receives the benefit of a 'child of their own'".⁶³ Furthermore, because both the surrogate and the intended parents encounter great adversity to bring a child into the world, liberal feminists reason that children born of surrogacy arrangements are the actual beneficiaries of such arrangements.⁶⁴

Radical feminists, on the other hand, opined, that surrogacy exploits both women and children.⁶⁵ In the argument that surrogacy commodifies women's reproductive abilities, it is likened to prostitution, where prostitutes sell their sexual services for payment, while surrogates offer their reproductive services for compensation.⁶⁶ Under the radical feminist theory, women do not exercise free choice in selling these services in the context of either prostitution or surrogacy. Rather, a woman chooses to do this, only in the sense that when a woman's sole alternatives are being poor or exploited, she may opt for exploitation as the lesser of two evils.⁶⁷

5. LEGAL ISSUES

Surrogacy throws up legal issues pertaining to paternity, maternity and contract problems.⁶⁸ These were exemplified in the case of Baby M in 1987. Baby M was born to a commissioning couple via surrogacy. The surrogate mother had artificial insemination with the sperm of the commissioning father, and the contract dictated that the woman handover the baby at birth, to the commissioning couple. This was done in 1986, when Baby M arrived. Less than 24 hours after handing over the baby, the surrogate mother demanded and collected back the baby from the commissioning parents. The couple consequently approached the court seeking legal custody. The

⁶⁰ Ibid.

⁶¹ Ibid.

⁶² Ibid at 68.

⁶³ Ibid.

⁶⁴ Ibid. 68-69

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Ibid.

⁶⁷ Ibid. at 65.

⁶⁸ Anu, Kumar P, Inder D, Sharma N. "Surrogacy and Women's Right to Health in India: Issues and Perspective", *Indian J Public Health* (2013), 57:65-70.

Supreme Court of New Jersey, formalized the surrogate arrangement between the parties and awarded custody of the baby to the commissioning parents. The court was said to have acted in the best interest of the baby.⁶⁹

After the events of this case, some States in the United States such as Florida developed a statute which included several provisions specifically designed to regulate surrogacy contracts. According to the statute, the following factors must be present in any surrogacy arrangement:

1. The intended parents, (who must be legally married) and the surrogate are 18 years of age or older; and
2. A physician determines that:
 - (a) the intended mother cannot physically gestate a pregnancy to term;
 - (b) the gestation will cause a risk to her health; or
 - (c) the gestation will cause a risk to the health of the foetus.⁷⁰

The statute further provides that the intended parents may compensate the surrogate only for the reasonable living, legal, and medical expenses in the prenatal, intrapartal, and postpartal periods.⁷¹

The Statute allows the surrogate to rescind the agreement to relinquish parental rights within seven days of the child's birth.⁷²

Surrogacy legislation in New Hampshire is even more comprehensive than that in Florida because it requires judicial pre-authorization of all surrogacy contracts.⁷³

Under the New Hampshire statute, the following conditions must be present for a surrogacy contract to obtain court approval:

1. The parties must have given their informed consent.
2. Psychological counselling and evaluations must have been completed.
3. The contract must not include any prohibited or unconscionable terms; and
4. The contract must be in the best interests of the intended child.⁷⁴

⁶⁹ *In re Baby M*, 525 A.2d 1128 (N.J. Super. Ct. Ch. Div. 1987), *aff'd in part and rev'd in part*, 537 A.2d 1227 (N.J. 1988).

⁷⁰ Flat. Stat. Ann. § 742.15 (West 1996).

⁷¹ *Ibid.*

⁷² *Ibid.*

⁷³ N. H. Rev. Stat. Ann. §§ 168-B:16 to 168-B:23 (1994 & Supp. 1997).

⁷⁴ *Ibid.*

In addition, all court-approved surrogacy arrangements must provide a right of rescission to the surrogate until 72 hours after the birth of the child.⁷⁵ In the event that the surrogate decides to keep the child, the parental rights of the intended parents are terminated, as is their obligation to provide financial support to the child.⁷⁶ If the surrogate does not decide to keep the child, her parental rights will automatically terminate and these same rights will be vested in the intended parents.⁷⁷

The New Hampshire statute prevents any entity from soliciting any party for purposes of entering into a surrogacy arrangement for compensation.⁷⁸

The Virginia statute differs from the New Hampshire statute in that it recognises two general types of surrogacy arrangement; those that are judicially pre-authorized and those that are not.⁷⁹ Under the statute, surrogacy contracts may be pre-authorized if the gestational mother is married and has had at least one successful pregnancy and if all parties, including the surrogate's husband, have signed the contract.⁸⁰

Before court approval of the contract, a home study of the intended parents, the surrogate, and the surrogate's husband must be conducted to ensure that all parties meet the standards of fitness applicable to adoptive parents.⁸¹ In addition, the Virginia statute requires all parties to undergo physical testing and psychological counselling.

In the United Kingdom, surrogate arrangement is illegal and is banned by the Surrogate Amendment Act of 1985. The surrogate mother maintains legal ownership of the child even in cases of gestational surrogacy, unless a parental order or adoption is made.⁸² Other countries, where it is illegal include Sweden, Finland, Japan, Saudi Arabia, and China.

⁷⁵ Ibid at § 168-B:25.

⁷⁶ Ibid.

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ N.H. Rev. Stat. Ann. §§ 168-B:16.

⁷⁹ Todd M. Krim, "Beyond Baby M: International Perspective on Gestational Surrogacy and the Demise of the Unitary Biological Mother," (1996) 5 *Annals Health L.* 193, 210.

⁸⁰ VA. Code Ann. § 20-160(B)(6) (Michie 1995). The intended child and the gestational surrogate are entitled to legal counsel at this stage.

⁸¹ Ibid. § 20-160(B)(8).

⁸² Serratelli A. "Surrogate Motherhood Contracts: Should the British or Canadian Model Fill the U.S. Legislative Vacuum?" *George Washington J Int Law Econ* (1993); 26:633-74.

In Australia and Canada, whereas altruistic (selfless help) surrogacy is legal, commercial surrogacy is not permitted under the law. In Canada, reimbursement for attendant expenses is permitted but other payments are illegal.⁸³

In Nigeria there are no legislative measures to regulate surrogacy in the country. Most artificial reproductive technology clinics in Nigeria base their operations on the Human Fertilization and Embryology Authority Guidelines of the United Kingdom.⁸⁴ However, the Nigerian Law Reform Commission has recommended that any child born to a woman as a result of artificial insemination or implantation of an embryo in the body of a woman while she is in a marriage must be regarded as a child of the husband.⁸⁵ The Commission further recommends that where a child is born under a surrogacy agreement, the commissioning parents should formally adopt the child, even if he is the biological child of the commissioning parents.⁸⁶ The rationale behind this is to prevent the surrogate mother from returning to claim the child.⁸⁷

A Bill for the establishment of a Nigerian Assisted Reproduction Authority was presented before the National Assembly in 2012 and was read for the second time on 2nd May 2012.⁸⁸ This Bill, however, was not passed into law as it did not enjoy the support of the majority of the legislators.

Subsequently, the National Health Act 8 of 2014 was enacted. Section 10 prohibits assisted reproductive technology by providing:

- (1) A person shall not
 - (a) manipulate any genetic material, including genetic material of human gametes, zygotes or embryos; or
 - (b) engage in any activity including nuclear transfer or embryo splitting for the purpose of the cloning of human being;
 - (c) import or export human zygotes or embryos.

⁸³ Legislative Council Standing Committee on Legislation, Parliament of Western Australia, Report on the Surrogacy Bill 2007 (2008) (Western Australian Report) 5 (4,12).

⁸⁴ J.O. Fadare & A.A. Adeniyi "Ethical Issues in Newer Assisted Reproductive Technologies: A View from Nigeria", (2015) 18 *Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice* S57, S59.

⁸⁵ Law Reform Commission "Reform of Nigerian Family Law", III, 15.

⁸⁶ *Ibid*, 16.

⁸⁷ Attah, M: (2016) "Family Welfare Law in Nigeria", 215.

⁸⁸ House of Representatives 'Votes and Proceedings' (2 May 2012) <http://nass.gov.ng/document/download/5555> Accessed 14 May, 2024 at 12:12pm.

- (2) A person who contravenes or fails to comply with the provision of this section commits an offence and is liable on conviction to imprisonment for a minimum of five years with no option of a fine.

It may be deduced from Section 10(1)(a) that assisted reproductive technology (ART) is prohibited. One cannot but wonder why several assisted reproductive technology practices, such as zygote intra-fallopian transfer (*in vitro* fertilisation) and gamete intra-allopien transfers, are widely practiced in major hospitals in the country, including the National Hospital, without any medical practitioner having been penalised so far.

6. ETHICAL ISSUES

i. Mistreatment of the mother

Whatever form it takes, surrogate motherhood is a form of reproductive prostitution.⁸⁹ The allegation is frequently made that one of the better analogies for surrogacy is reproductive prostitution. The woman sells or rents her body or body parts. The relation is impersonal. She is told to do what she is told. The surrogate that is picked is on the basis of her desirable qualities: appearance, health, and fertility. She is paid to provide her body for a period of time, and then she is to disappear.

ii. Exploitation of the Surrogate

One of Ghandhi's 'Seven Deadly Sins' was "Commerce without morality". He would be grieved to learn that his home nation of India is now known as the surrogacy hub of the world because surrogacy costs are so low there. For years, poor Indian women have been exploited by rich Western couples, and surrogacy is now a multibillion-dollar industry in that nation. Because of rampant abuses, the Indian government has moved to ban the practice of commercial surrogacy, while allowing it to continue only for closely related relatives. This move, of course, has raised howls of protest from homosexuals who want children, and from some feminists who have trotted out the old tired slogan that women should be able to do whatever they want with their own bodies – even if they are being ruthlessly abused and misused.⁹⁰ Most studies claim that feelings of regret among surrogates are rare, but the high-profile custody battles

⁸⁹ Thomas A. Shannon "Ethical Issues in Artificial Reproduction" *Conscience*, September/October 1989, Volume X, No.5, p.12-13.

⁹⁰ "India Unveils Plan to Ban Surrogacy". BBC News, August 25, 2016.

between surrogates and intended parents seem to indicate that there is a lot that is not being revealed by the medical establishment.

iii. Abortion

Interestingly, most contracts between the surrogate and the commissioning parents insist that the surrogate abort the child if genetic tests show abnormalities unacceptable to the commissioning parents – in direct conflict with the surrogate’s alleged ‘right to choose’.⁹¹ Proponents of surrogate motherhood deny any infringement of rights, of course, because they say that the baby in question is mere property under contract.

iv. The Interests of the Child

God designed the family in a way that serves the best interests of the child, and an abundance of peer-reviewed research confirms that this arrangement is the most advantageous for children in all aspects of their beings – physical, mental, emotional and spiritual. Surrogacy introduces a fracturing influence that can be very detrimental to a child whose parental figures are multiplied. Such children may have as many as three mothers (egg donor, surrogate and adoptive) and two fathers (sperm donor and adoptive).⁹²

In response to a question about whether surrogate motherhood is morally licit, the Vatican’s Congregation for the Doctrine of the Faith replied in its document *Donum Vitae*:

No, for the same reasons which lead one to reject artificial fertilisation: For it is contrary to the unity of marriage and to the dignity of the procreation of the human person. Surrogate motherhood represents an objective failure to meet the obligations of maternal love, of conjugal fidelity and of responsible motherhood; it offends the dignity and the right of the child to be conceived, carried in the womb, brought into the world and brought up by his own parents. It sets up, to the detriment of

⁹¹ Donald DeMarco, “*In My Mother’s Womb: The Catholic Church’s Defence of Natural Life*”, Manassas, Virginia: Trinity Communications (1997), p.181.

⁹² <<https://www.npr.org/templates/story/story.php?storyId=127981206>> accessed 14 May, 2024 at 9:06 am.

families, a division between the physical, psychological and moral elements which constitute those families.⁹³

For the reasons already described, the Catechism of the Catholic Church reiterates this principle: “Techniques that entail the dissociation of husband and wife, by the intrusion of a person other than the couple (donation of sperm or ovum, surrogate uterus) are gravely immoral.”⁹⁴

v. Coercion/Undue Influence

Coercion here does not necessarily imply the influence of another person on the surrogate. One may be coerced or forced into a surrogacy agreement by his/her compromised economic condition. The desire to alleviate suffering or the family may be a motive. It might also be possible that the male spouses may unduly influence or coerce the surrogate mother into the agreement, considering the huge financial benefit implicit on it. Who determines the financial package involved in a surrogacy arrangement? Some, if not all of the surrogacy arrangements are made by an agency driven by profit. Many interests are served by the arrangement, all dependent on the acquiescence of the surrogate mother. She might thus be influenced unduly by overblown financial packages. It is also possible that surrogacy agents may exploit the vulnerability of both surrogate mothers and intending parents.⁹⁵

vi. Disclosure/Confidentiality

Involvement of a third party in the surrogacy arrangement means the privacy and security in a two-party arrangement are compromised.⁹⁶ Surrogacy arrangement also entails total disclosure of personal medical history and conditions by the potential surrogate mother to the physician during evaluation, who may subsequently disclose the same to the intending parents. In so doing, confidentiality between physician and client may be breached, where the potential mother may not want some aspects revealed.

⁹³ <

https://www.vatican.va/roman_curia/congregations/cfaith/documents/rc_con_cfaith_doc_19870222_respect-for-human-life_en.html> accessed 15 May, 2024 at 9:18am.

⁹⁴ <https://www.hli.org/resources/catechism-of-the-catholic-church-ivf/> accessed 15 May, 2024 at 9:23am.

⁹⁵ Saravanan S. “An Ethnomethodological Approach to Examine Exploitation in the Context of Capacity, Trust and Experience of Commercial Surrogacy in India”, *Philos Ethics Humanit Med* (2013); 8:10.

⁹⁶ Frankel S. “Postmodern Procreation: A Cultural Account of Assisted Reproduction”. In Ginsbury FD, Rapping R, Editors, “*Conceiving the New World Order: The Global Politics of Reproduction*”. (1995) Berkeley (USA): University of California Press.

Children from surrogacy may want to have full disclosure of their parentage in later years. Would it be ethically correct not to fully disclose their origin to them, including who carried them "in utero"? Such disclosure especially when there is a genetic link may be medically invaluable. Complications may arise where the surrogate mother declined such disclosure ab initio at the contract level, or where all contact links between the parties were severed.

vii. Religious Views

Nigerians have different religious inclinations. The acceptability or not, of the concept of surrogacy and issues consequent upon that, may vary from one belief to the other. Opinions among Christian groups differ. For the Catholic Church, a child is a gift, and not a right and procreation can only result from the conjugal love of married people. They describe as "gravely immoral" any technique that entails the dissociation of a married couple, by the intrusion of a person other than the couple including gamete donation and surrogacy. The church further states that surrogacy violates the dignity of the child.⁹⁷

Protestant denominations have a more liberal attitude to infertility treatments and surrogacy, express reservations about probable challenges arising from it such as future psychological problems for the child and questions regarding ownership of the child.⁹⁸

Islam has varying views on surrogacy. Some Muslim scholars tend to view surrogacy through the provisions of the Shariah law, while some adjudge it as similar to prostitution as it entails an alien woman carrying a child who is not her legal husband's own. It implies that such a child may be deemed illegitimate. For some, however, the responsibility of humans to procreate and preserve the human race makes surrogacy permissible for infertile couples.⁹⁹

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

- i). There is a need in Nigeria, for legal provisions for or against surrogacy. Such laws must provide for the legality or otherwise of the different types and forms of surrogacy taking into consideration the social, traditional, cultural, ethical, and psychological climate in the country. It should be able to regulate the

⁹⁷ Mckenzie E: "Religious Views on Surrogacy: Opposing Views". <http://www.people.opposingviews.com/religious-views-surrogacy-9339.html>. Accessed 15 May, 2024 at 10:43am.

⁹⁸ Ibid.

⁹⁹ Ibid.

procedure and processes of commercial surrogacy to avoid exploitation of a vulnerable population by surrogacy agents, while serving the interest of all concerned.

- ii). Disparities in the regulations of surrogacy arrangements by countries create difficulties for the enforcement of a foreign surrogacy in another jurisdiction, although generally, legal considerations have always been in favour of the best interests of the child. Considering the fact that intending couples travel outside their countries in search of surrogates, it is imperative for the international community or bodies to come together and put in place an international surrogacy instrument in order to minimise complications that could arise from international surrogate contracts.
- iii). The age limit for an intending surrogate mother should be pegged between 21 and 35 years, which is the age range under the Indian Surrogacy (Regulation) Bill 2016. This will help in addressing possible health complications associated with late child bearing in older women.

8. CONCLUSION

Surrogacy arrangement through assisted reproductive technology (ART) process is a fast growing area in medical and biomedical sciences across the globe. Due to huge pressure, mostly from family members and friends, on couples to have children after marriages, infertile couples have resorted to having their own children through ART in order to avoid social stigmatization. Similarly, commercial surrogacy has made it feasible for women who have no genetic links to the foetuses they gestate to enjoy monetary benefits and rewards for acting as gestational surrogate mothers to the intended parents or commissioning couples. Surrogacy, as a form of artificial reproduction, has sparked numerous medico-legal and ethical controversies. Some argue that surrogacy arrangements undermine the self-worth of both the child, who is viewed as an object of a "settlement commodity," and the surrogate mother, who is reduced to a "womb for rent," while the act of procreation is transformed into a "commercial enterprise."¹⁰⁰

¹⁰⁰ Abdullah, F.M: "Legal and Ethical Aspects Beyond Commercial Surrogacy: Modern Form of Human Trafficking" (2019) 22(1) *Journal of Legal Ethical and Regulatory Issues*, pp. 1-7.

The unregulated surrogacy practice in Nigeria has invariably opened the floodgates to a number of unethical practices by medical experts to exploit susceptible donors and surrogate mothers who may be engaged by fertility clinics to either ‘harvest their eggs’ (sell their eggs) or ‘hire their wombs’ for insignificant payments¹⁰¹ as well as subject intending commissioning couples to undue societal stigmatization and uncertainty regarding their parenthood status of the surrogate children.

¹⁰¹ Joel, M: “Ovum Trading: Inside Nigeria’s Multi-million Naira Human Egg Business”, (9 August 2015) *The Punch*. <https://punchng.com/ovum-trading-inside-nigerias-multi-million-naira-human-egg-business/>. Accessed 14th Many, 2024 at 11:10am.